

Self-assessment survey for Citizen Social Science projects

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Welcome to the Citizen Science Self-Assessment questionnaire developed by the CoAct project!

This questionnaire helps you to reflect upon and evaluate your citizen science project and/or proposal and has a focus on Citizen Social Science.

It is a tool that investigates

A) the operationalisation of projects/proposals

B) the expected outcomes & impact

This is done for three dimensions:

1) on the level of science and scientists,

2) on the level of citizens, engaged actors and organisations,

3) on the level of socio-ecological and socio-economic aspects

When going through the questions, please be aware that your project/proposal cannot be strong in all aspects covered in this self-assessment. It is natural that projects have strengths in certain areas, while other areas are of less importance. Thus the aim of this questionnaire is not to judge a project but rather to reflect on its Citizen Social Science approach and expected outcomes.

The questionnaire is for your own use and should help you see where you stand with your project/proposal. This goal can be accomplished best if you answer honestly to all questions.

There are 37 questions in this survey

Introduction

Please remember: this questionnaire is a self-assessment tool. There are no right or wrong answers. It is for your own use and should help you to see where you stand with your project/proposal.

There are 3 main Sections (and each one has part A and part B):

1. Science and scientists
2. Citizens, engaged actors and organisations
3. Socio-ecological and socio-economic aspects

Please use the open field questions after each block to document your discussion and note down anything you might feel of relevance for the specific aspect.

<p>What is the name or acronym of your Citizen Science project, initiative, or proposal?</p>		
<p>Operationalisation of dimension 1: Science</p> <p>This first block of questions addresses the scientific aspects of Citizen Social Science projects.</p> <p>This part looks at how the scientific process is set up and what impact you expect from the joint scientific work with citizens and other related actors.</p> <p>Please rate the following statements for your project.</p>		
<p>Scientific objectives</p>		
<p>The scientific goals are sufficiently clear for the engaged stakeholders and authentic. [1=strongly disagree, 7= strongly agree]</p>		
<p>The scientific objectives can be reached by involving citizens and other relevant actors in the scientific process. [1=strongly disagree, 7= strongly agree]</p>		
<p>The scientific objectives address socially relevant problems. [1=strongly disagree, 7= strongly agree]</p>		
<p>Please reflect briefly on your scientific objectives and what kind of social issues they address?</p>		
<p>Data & Technology</p>		
<p>The project follows clear and transparent ethical guidelines. [1=strongly disagree, 7= strongly agree]</p>		
<p>The project has a data management and privacy protection plan. [1=strongly disagree, 7= strongly agree]</p>		
<p>The project has a technical interface to connect to other data sources or platforms (e.g. for data exchange). [1=strongly disagree, 7= strongly agree]</p>		
<p>The generated knowledge and data is shared publicly, given that this is in accordance with ethical and scientific guidelines. [1=strongly disagree, 7= strongly agree]</p>		
<p>Please reflect briefly on your ethical guidelines, data management and related aspects?</p>		
<p>Evaluation & Adaptation</p>		
<p>The project has an evaluation concept to assess scientific outcomes. [1=strongly disagree, 7= strongly agree]</p>		
<p>The project has a participatory evaluation approach, giving a voice to the participants in the evaluation design, process and results. [1=strongly disagree, 7= strongly agree]</p>		

Feedback and evaluation results are periodically taken up by adaptive project management. [1=strongly disagree, 7= strongly agree]		
Please elaborate briefly on your evaluation concept to assess the scientific outcome? What is your main scientific question and how do you plan to assess it?		
Co-operations & synergies		
The project fosters co-operation with other projects and initiatives. [1=strongly disagree, 7= strongly agree]		
The project connects experts from different disciplines / social fields / sectors. [1=strongly disagree, 7= strongly agree]		
Please reflect briefly on how your project cooperates with other organisations, projects and initiatives? Are you connected to relevant stakeholders? How?		
Impact of dimension 1: Science		
The following questions assess the potential scientific impact of the project.		
If you are still at the beginning of your project, please give some first indications of the potential impact.		
Scientific knowledge & publications		
Research results are actively contributing to the scientific discourse (e.g. via scientific publications, blogs, etc.). [1=strongly disagree, 7= strongly agree]		
Participating actors are included in publications either actively or their contributions are recognised in the publications. [1=strongly disagree, 7= strongly agree]		
Scientific project results are taken up by other projects. [1=strongly disagree, 7= strongly agree]		
The project leads to new research questions, new projects or proposals. [1=strongly disagree, 7= strongly agree]		
Please reflect briefly on your strategy for dissemination & exploitation of your scientific results. In which formats and for which target groups are you publishing your results? Where and how are the project results being taken up?		
Knowledge transfer		

<p>The knowledge of the participants contributed to expanding the scientific knowledge base. [1=strongly disagree, 7= strongly agree]</p>	
<p>The project contributes to a mutual understanding of science and society. [1=strongly disagree, 7= strongly agree]</p>	
<p>How sustainable, do you think, is the established knowledge transfer? And where do you see most potential for a sustainable knowledge transfer?</p>	
<p>Operationalisation of dimension 2: Citizens/engaged actors</p> <p>This second block of questions addresses the engagement of citizens and any other relevant actors in the scientific process. These other actors might be NGOs, associations that represent a specific interest group, Civic Society Associations, SMEs, etc.</p> <p>Please rate the following statements for your project/proposal.</p>	
<p>Target group alignment & options for involvement</p>	
<p>The project's objectives (also non-scientific) are jointly developed and agreed with participants, clear and authentic. [1=strongly disagree, 7= strongly agree]</p>	
<p>The project offers a variety of options to get involved (depending on interests, availability, knowledge, ...). [1=strongly disagree, 7= strongly agree]</p>	
<p>Participants can choose to engage in various project phases (e.g. during definition of research questions, data gathering, data analysis, dissemination of results). [1=strongly disagree, 7= strongly agree]</p>	
<p>Please reflect briefly on your engaged actors: Who are direct participants of the project, who are relevant other stakeholders and who are target audiences? How are they engaging? What formats proved particularly well for inclusive and balanced participation?</p>	
<p>Supporting material & communication</p>	
<p>Supporting material is aligned according to different target groups (e.g. age, language, ...). [1=strongly disagree, 7= strongly agree]</p>	
<p>The different project roles and responsibilities (e.g. scientific lead, community engagement coordinator, etc.) are transparent and clear to all participants. [1=strongly disagree, 7= strongly agree]</p>	

Citizen participants can directly interact and communicate with scientists and other project actors . [1=strongly disagree, 7= strongly agree]		
Please reflect briefly on your communication strategy with your engaged actors: when and how are you communicating with them and is the communication two-ways (e.g. can it also be initiated by the participants?) Have you noticed any changes in actors' roles in the project?		
<p>Outcome & impact of dimension 2: Citizens/engaged actors</p> <p>The following questions address the impact of the project on the individual participants.</p> <p>If you are still at the beginning of your project, you can give some first indications of the impact you expect.</p>		
Knowledge, skills & competencies		
Participants achieved a personal learning outcome. [1=strongly disagree, 7= strongly agree]		
The project contributes to a better understanding of science and its processes. [1=strongly disagree, 7= strongly agree]		
The project contributes to a better understanding of the specific issues of concern amongst the participants. [1=strongly disagree, 7= strongly agree]		
Participants achieved a personal benefit (other than mentioned above). [1=strongly disagree, 7= strongly agree]		
Please reflect briefly on what kind of learnings or personal benefits participants achieved or will achieve?		
Responsibility, ownership & engagement		
The project fosters ownership and responsibility for the socio-environmental project goals amongst the participants. [1=strongly disagree, 7= strongly agree]		
The project contributes to a personal change in behaviour amongst project participants. [1=strongly disagree, 7= strongly agree]		
The participants are motivated to continue the project or get involved in similar activities. [1=strongly disagree, 7= strongly agree]		
Please reflect briefly on how and when this perceived ownership, responsibility and change in behaviour is taking place? Are there any kinds of activities continued by the participants? Are there certain participants more inclined to keep involved? Also, please add your observations if you notice other		

forms of engagement emerging with any engaged group of actors or stakeholders.	
<p>Operationalisation of dimension 3: Socio-ecological, socio-economic aspects</p> <p>The third part of the questionnaire is dedicated to the outreach to the wider public audience. It looks into the communication measures for the general public and also the potential impact of the Citizen Social Science project on society at large, the ecology and economy.</p> <p>Please rate the following statements for your project.</p>	
<p>Dissemination & outreach</p>	
The project makes use of different media to reach a wide public audience (e.g. print, online, social media, etc.). [1=strongly disagree, 7= strongly agree]	
Project results are made available in appropriate formats tailored to the respective target audience (e.g via videos, etc.). [1=strongly disagree, 7= strongly agree]	
The project includes innovative methods for dissemination (e.g. co-operation with artists, etc.). [1=strongly disagree, 7= strongly agree]	
There is a contact point offered for the general public for any questions or further project information. [1=strongly disagree, 7= strongly agree]	
Please reflect briefly on your dissemination and outreach approach: Have you found any very successful or unsuccessful way of communicating with the wider public about your Citizen Social Science research? What worked, what didn't? What was particularly innovative?	
<p>Co-operations & synergies</p>	
The project leverages existing networks and Civil Society Organisations for dissemination. [1=strongly disagree, 7= strongly agree]	
The project creates or supports interfaces between science and Civil Society Organisations. [1=strongly disagree, 7= strongly agree]	
Please reflect briefly on synergies and cooperation with non-scientific and/or Civil Society Organisations? Is there something that worked especially well or that turned out to be very difficult?	

Impact of dimension 3: Socio-ecological, socio-economic aspects	
The following questions assess the potential impact of the project on society, ecology and economy.	
If you are still at the beginning of your project, please give some first estimations about the potential impact.	
Collective capacity	
The project creates or fosters a community / collective. [1=strongly disagree, 7= strongly agree]	
The project increases resilience and the capacity of the involved community to advocate common goals. [1=strongly disagree, 7= strongly agree]	
The project supports wider societal goals, such as the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), or others. [1=strongly disagree, 7= strongly agree]	
Please elaborate briefly on the societal goals or collective capacity that the project is fostering?	
Political impact	
The project stimulates the discourse between political representatives and the engaged actors in the project. [1=strongly disagree, 7= strongly agree]	
Project results have an impact on political decisions, procedures or political institutions. [1=strongly disagree, 7= strongly agree]	
Please briefly elaborate: How do you see any political impact evolving from your project?	
Ecological impact	
The project supports measures to protect natural resources, to counteract pollution, or deal with any other environmentally sustainable aspects. [1=strongly disagree, 7= strongly agree]	
The project contributes to a better public understanding of environmental topics. [1=strongly disagree, 7= strongly agree]	
Please reflect briefly on the socio-ecological impact your project creates?	
Sustainability (social, economic, ecological impact)	
The project has a clear plan on how to sustain and make use of the results after the project ends to create further social, economic or ecological impact. [1=strongly disagree, 7= strongly agree]	
Project results are transferable to other contexts. [1=strongly disagree, 7= strongly agree]	
Please reflect briefly on the transferability and wider sustainability of your project results? In which context do	

you see this taking place, e.g. at the level of concerned communities?	
Economic potential	
The project generates economic impact, such as cost reduction, new job creation, new markets, new business models, etc. [1=strongly disagree, 7= strongly agree]	
Please reflect briefly on what kind of economic or socio-economic impact the project creates or expects to create?	
Does the project deliver concrete tools to meet any political, socio-economic or ecological challenges. If so, could you briefly describe them?	
Do you have any other comments you would like to share? Any other considerations regarding your Citizen Social Science approach that have not been covered so far?	